

Organizational Justice and Academic Staff Performance among Public and Private Tertiary Institutions in South-South States of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The organizational conflicts among employers and employees in tertiary institutions most especially public institutions has remained a recurring spike in Nigeria that undermine the overall performance of lecturers and students outcomes in the institutions. The specific objective of this research is to investigate the extent of significant differences in organizational justice among lecturers in public and private universities in relation to academic staff commitment in tertiary institutions in South-South States in Nigeria which is also in line with the research question and hypothesis. The research adopted a descriptive survey research design, the population of the study is 400. Factorial analysis of variance was used to test hypothesis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Cronbach alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument. The findings revealed that there is level of significant differences in interactional justice in relations to lecturer students relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-South Nigeria, in conclusion equitable distribution of resources, fair procedures for job decisions, with appropriate allocation of resources and fair communication of decisions will result in high academic staff performance towards higher academic excellence. The researcher recommends among others that management of both public and private universities should come out with supportive policies as a way of promoting interactional justice toward maintaining lecturer-student relationship which can be done through integrating the philosophy of target education programme established in 1990 by Aumua and Drake (2002).

KEYWORDS: *Organizational Justice, Interactional Justice, Academic Staff Performance and Public and Private Tertiary Institutions*

1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a very demanding professions such that the success of the educational institutions depends on highly committed and dedicated Lecturers. In Nigeria, the teaching profession is encumbered with a lot of injustices that have the capacity of lowering the level of commitment of lecturers towards attaining quality academic delivery. These injustices occur in terms of distributive justice, procedural justice, informational justice and interactional justice which determine the extent to which academic staff perceive organizational justice in relation to their performance in the institutions.

However, academic staff are not satisfied with the ways rewards are being apportioned which is not proportional to inputs based on the principle of equity. The evaluation of academic staff performance and reward in terms of wages, promotions, work roles and workloads are not fairly distributed, which invariably affects their level of affective commitment to performance. The universities managements do not properly apply the principles of distributive justice to allocation of rules based on equality, equity and needs of academic staff.

Moreover, the procedure used to allocate rewards and benefits to academic staff is not fair, which affects their emotional and psychological impact on the courses they handle. The decision criteria and control process at the workplace are not fair, which makes it look biased, inaccurate, lack relationship, lack representation of all concerned and inconsistent with ethical norms and indirectly affect the extent of input of academic staff in their respective subject areas. It is clear that in private institutions in Nigeria, the decision to allocate rewards and take decisions rests solely on the owners of private institutions without prior consultation of academic staff. Thus, the question remains whether such experience is found in public universities, and if found, to what degree compare with experiences of lecturers in public universities in South-South, Nigeria. Though, lack of adoption of appropriate and generally acceptable procedures for rewards has affected the level of cognitive, affective, behavioural reaction, psychological wellbeing with feeling of reputation of life satisfaction and subject knowledge among academic staff in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria.

How to cite this paper: Musah Ishaq | Prof. Lilian O. Orogbu | Dr. Ndubuisi-Okolo Purity U. "Organizational Justice and Academic Staff Performance among Public and Private Tertiary Institutions in South-South States of Nigeria" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-2, February 2020, pp.1042-1055, URL:

www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30205.pdf

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The evaluation of employee performance in the Nigerian tertiary institutions especially academic staff can be assessed in terms of the degree of commitment to academic performance, lecturers' degree of subject knowledge of the courses taken, level of communication skill and lecturer-student relationship among academic staff in the tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria. These variables determine the level of academic staff performance in relation to organizational justice in both the private and public tertiary institutions in Nigeria; commitment is the relative strength of lecture's identification with and involvement in a particular institution. Academic staff level of commitment has three components, namely: a lecturer's belief in and acceptance of institution's goals and values; his/her willingness to work towards accomplishing the institution's goals; his/her strong desire to continue as institution's member.

Also, lecturer's subject knowledge (competence) remains one of the major determinants of students' academic achievements. Teaching is a collaborative process which encompasses interaction by both learners and the lecturer. Lecturer subject knowledge in teaching process is a multidimensional concept that measures numerous interrelated aspects of sharing knowledge with learners which include communication skills, subject matter expertise, lecturer attendance, teaching skills and lecturer attitude which revolve around the extent academic staff perceive organizational justice in the institutions. As lecturers spend an incredible amount of time with their students over the course of the year, it is the responsibility of lecturers to foster an inclination for learning and this can be done when they perceive procedural justice in relation to their input as obtainable in other tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Studies have revealed that the relationship between lecturers and students is an important predictor of academic engagement and achievement. In fact, the most powerful weapon lecturers have when trying to foster a favorable learning climate is positive relationships with their students. Students who perceive their teachers as more supportive have better achievement outcomes (Boynton & Boynton, 2005). Additionally, the learning environment plays a significant role in maintaining student interest and engagement. When students feel a sense of control and security in the classroom, they are more engaged because they approach learning with enthusiasm. Students become active participants in their own education (Skinner & Green, 2008). Therefore, the first step to helping a student become more motivated and engaged, and thus academically successful, is building and maintaining positive lecturer-student relationships which can justify a perception of procedural justice (Maulana, Opdenakker, Stroet, & Bosker, 2013). The general objective of the study is to determine the extent of significant difference in organisational justice in relation to academic staff performance between public and private universities in South-South Nigeria.

In the light of above scenario, and in order to fill the gap the study intends to compare the extent of Significant difference in organizational justice among lecturers in public and private universities in relation to academic staff performance in tertiary institutions in South-South states Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study is to determine the extent of significant difference in organisational justice in relation to academic staff performance between public and private universities in South-South Nigeria. The specific objective is:

A. To investigate if there is variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturer's-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-South Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Interactional Justice

The third dimension of organizational justice is interactional justice. (Bies & Moag, 2008). Interactional justice exist when decision makers treat people with respect and sensitivity and explain the rationale for decisions thoroughly. Therefore, interactional justice is the treatment that an individual or employee receives as decision made (Colquitt, 2001).

It concerns the fairness of the interpersonal treatment individuals are given during the implementation of procedures. Cropanzano, Prehar and Chen (2007) simply refer to interactional justice as "usually operationalized as one-to-one transactions between individuals". According to Bies (2008), interactional justice focuses on employees' perceptions of the interpersonal behaviour exercised during the representation of decisions and procedures. Interactional justice is related to the quality of relationships between individuals within organizations (Folger & Cropanzano, 2008). Although some scholars view interactional justice as a single construct, others have proposed two dimensions of interactional justice (Bies, 2008; Lind & Tyler, 2008). The two dimensions of interactional justice proposed are interpersonal and informational justice. These two dimensions of interactional justice are related to each other. However, research recommends that both concepts should be looked at differently since they have differential consequence on justice perceptions (Colquitt, 2001 ;).

In some respects, interactional justice falls under the umbrella term of procedural justice, but is significant enough to be considered in its own right. It refers to the quality of the interpersonal treatment received by those working in organization, particularly as part of formal decision making procedures. Bies and moag (2008) identify some key aspects of interactional justice, which can enhance people's perceptions of fair treatment, as follows:

- **Truthfulness:** Information that is given must be realistic and accurate, and presented in an open and forthright manner.
- **Respect:** Employees should be treated with dignity, with no recourse to insults or discourteous behaviour.
- **Propriety:** Questions and statements should never be 'improper' or involve prejudicial elements such as racism or sexism.
- **Justification:** When a perceived injustice has occurred, giving a 'social account' such as an explanation or apology can reduce or eliminate the sense of anger generated.
- **Authority:** Perceptions about a manager's authority can affect procedural justice judgement. Three aspects of authority having a bearing on this judgement are trust, neutrality and standing (Lind and Tyler, 2008). Managers will be considered trustworthy if their

intentions are clear and fair and their behaviour congruent with these intentions. Neutrality refers to the use of facts to make an unbiased decision, while standing implies a recognition accorded to managers who treat others with dignity, politeness and respect for their rights.

Figure 1: Organizational Justice Relationship with Academic Staff Performance

Source: Cropanzano, R., Bowen, D. E. & Gilliland, S. W. (2007). *The Management of Organisational Justice. Academy of Management Perspectives*, 21, 34-48.

2.1.1. Academic Staff (Employee) Performance

Performance has been the most vital issue for every organization, either profit or non-profit organisation. It is expedient for managers to know the factors that affect the performance. However, it is quite difficult in actual sense to measure performance, but in this context, performance is taken to be the productivity that is, the relationship between input and output (Ebhote, 2015).

Performance is defined as a degree of viability of achieving predetermined Organizational objective (Chan & Baum, 2007). For instance, employee performance says a college professor is evaluated on three functions: teaching, research and community service. Therefore, the job outcome of a Professor is a measure of his/her performance in a job. Generally speaking, employees performance on the job is equal to the sum of performance recorded on the major job functions or activities (Bernardin, 2010). According to Chan and Quarles (2012), performance encompasses both quantitative and qualitative measurement of efforts and is used to achieve the aim of an organization. Performance encompasses processes such as; goal setting, measurement, assessment, feedback, rewarding for excellent results, use of corrective measures in situation of bad result (Kaplan, 2001; Chang, 2006). Lawrie and Gobbold (2004) stated that performance is an important guidance in respect to the expectations of the employees and goals of the organization in general. According to the authors, this guidance is used by both public and private sector organizations to maintain their competitiveness with respect to other firms. Aim of performance measurement is focused on: increasing employees job satisfaction, motivation, providing on time and quick feedback, providing fairness in the structure of the organization, providing equal employee opportunities, and helping them improve themselves (Griffith, 2003).

Employee is a person who is hired for a wage, salary, fee or payment to perform work for an employer (Balyan, 2012). Both private and public sector organizations are established to achieve corporate goals using resources such as men, machines, materials and money. All these resources are important, but most important among them are the employees.

Nowadays, majority of firms are competing favorably with one another in business environment to maintain large market shares and firms who valued their employees always take the lead in its market. The role of employees on the job is vital for the growth of any organization. The performance of employees on different jobs through mutual effort is needed for the success of any unit/department. The nature of relationships that employees have with their supervisors or co-workers in the organization affects their commitment towards work and organizational performance either positively or negatively. Employees commitment towards work and organizational performance affects negatively management policy in deciding work assignments and opportunities in the workplace without fairness among employees (Griffeth & Gaertner, 2000; Ellen et al. 2001). When some employees perceive that their boss uses favoritism to please one party against the other in the workplace, their morale towards work will be relatively low. The top manager is the most important as the enabler of the employee commitment to jobs and to the organization (Corporate Leadership Council, 2004).

In spite of this, Levin and Rosse (2001) wrote that developing an effective working relationship with employees is considered one of the most effective ways that managers can retain employees in the organization, and use of non-monetary recognition in form of acknowledgment from co-workers and managers is very important.

According to Daniel (2010), employee performance can be defined in terms of whether employees' behaviors contribute to organizational goals. Performance can be seen as an individual, group, or organizational task performance. However, an employees job consists of a number of interrelated tasks, duties, and responsibilities which a job holder needs to carry out, whereas performance is a behavior or action that is relevant for the organization's goals and that can be measured in terms of the level of proficiency or contribution to goals that is represented by a particular or set of actions (Campbell, 2007). Employee performance is normally looked at in terms of outcomes.

2.1.2. Lecturer-student Relationship

Many researchers assume lecturer-student relationships to be determinants of students' academic outcomes and, so, measure the effects of these relationships on different academic parameters. For instance, Hamre and Pianta (2001) found evidences of lecturer-student relationship conflict evaluated in the first grade on achievement seven years later, controlling for relevant baseline child characteristics. Connell and Wellborn (1991), Deci and Ryan (2000), in their investigation found that the role of relations with lecturers in students' academic attainment variables emanates extensively from the Self-Determination Theory (SDT). This theory is used as a theoretical framework that links teacher-student interactions with students' engagement and, consequently, their achievement. Of special importance for the purpose of this study is a mini-theory within SDT called Basic Needs Theory (Rani, Garg, & Rastogi 2012) that assumes three basic psychological needs: competence, autonomy and relatedness. The social context can either support or thwart these needs, thereby positively or negatively affecting students' engagement. Based on this theory, teachers' participation is important for satisfying the need for relatedness between organizational justice and

academic staff performance. This mean to the degree of quality interpersonal relations with students and is manifested through teachers having time for students, being flexible to their needs and expressing positive feelings toward them through perception of organizational justice. Many researchers found that lecturers' interpersonal relationship with management and students seems to be the strongest predictor of lecturers' academic achievement among all of the other presumably important dimensions of lecturer' behavior, attitude and action in perception of organizational justice; the students of highly involved lecturer perceive their teachers not only as involved but also as giving more structure and support to students' autonomy, independently of the lecturer actual behavior in these two dimensions (Furrer and Skinner 2003; Skinner and Belmont 1993). Meanwhile, the meta-analysis from Stroet, Opendakker and Minnaert (2013) actually support that interactional justice positively relate to lecturer-student relationship since students also assess organizational justice through their lecturer's interaction on daily academic activities. Based on a systematic review of the evidence on the effects of need supportive teaching on early adolescents' academic motivation and engagement, the researchers affirmed that, although results revealed positive relations of each of the three dimensions of need supportive teaching with students' motivation and engagement, there search on their unique importance is scarce and needs further investigation.

Moreover, the relationship between students' need for relatedness and their academic outcomes is clearly documented. The sense of relatedness tapped by the measures of school climate and the quality of teacher-student relations, as well as the feelings of belonging, acceptance, importance, and interpersonal support, are related to important academic outcomes, including positive effect (Skinner and Belmont, 1993), effort and self-efficacy (Sakiz et al., 2012), engagement (Furrer and Skinner, 2003; Skinner and Belmont, 1993; Wu et al., 2010), self-reported academic initiative (Danielsen et al., 2010), interest in school (Wentzel, 1998), self-regulated learning (Rani, Garg & Rastogi 2012), and grades (Furrer and Skinner, 2003; Niehaus et al. 2012; Wu et al., 2010). Studies on effect of academic achievement on lecturer-student relationship that investigated the relation between lecturer-student relationships and academic achievement usually test for the reciprocal effect of achievement on lecturer-student relationships. They found that a positive significant relationship exists between teacher-student relationship with interactional justice in the institution due to closeness and exchange of ideas and knowledge the students derive from their lecturers. However, some studies investigated the role of students' characteristics (including academic achievement) in the formation of lecturers' preference for students. Lecturers prefer an institution where aspects of organizational justice are implemented to the letter which influence their intimate relationship with the students. Lecturer acceptance or preference is defined as the extent to which a lecturer likes a specific student (Mercer and DeRosier, 2010) and is usually expressed in lecturers' differential interactions with students, although lecturers may not be aware of this unequal treatment. This reasoning assumes a directionality of influence that is opposite to the one mentioned as students' achievement is considered as

predictor and lecturers' perception is considered as outcome.

This dependent variable (lecturer-student relationship) has received some empirical support such as students' academic achievement which was found to contribute to lecturers' perceptions of their students (Aluja-Fabregat, Balleste-Almacellas and Torrubia-Beltri, 1999) and lecturers prefer students with higher achievements (Davis, 2006; Kuklinski and Weinstein, 2001).

The question of directionality of influence of lecturer-student relationship in terms of lecturers' expectations and students' achievement was addressed in the study of Crano and Mellon (1978).

The findings suggest that lecturers' expectations cause students' academic achievement positively where they perceive higher level of full implementation of organizational justice. This invariably is the mediating role of student perceptions and assessment of lecturers by students. The relation between lecturers' acceptance expressed in teachers' differential behavior which is characterized by interactional justice toward students and their academic outcomes can operate directly without involving students' interpretative processes. However, the contributions of teachers' perceptions to changes in students' academic outcomes are probably mediated through students' perceptions of their lecturers' support (Kuklinski and Weinstein 2001; Skinner et al. 2008). This mediation depends on two conditions: (1) the differences in lecturer acceptance of students are expressed in the degree of lecturers' supportive behavior and (2) students have the capacity to perceive the expressed level of teacher support. With regard to the first condition, Babad (1993) reported a discrepancy in students' and lecturers' perception of lecturers' emotional support for students regarding their achievement: students perceived that the high achievers receive more emotional support from their lecturers which is an indication of fairly interactional justice perceived by lecturers whereas lecturers reported being more supportive toward low achievers. Although both perspectives can be regarded as valid, this result could also imply the possibility that lecturers are unaware of their differential behavior. Also, Kuklinski and Weinstein (2001) reported that lecturers differ in their propensities to treat high and low achievers differently: in some classrooms, lecturers' differential behavior is more salient than in others. The second condition, i.e. students' capacity to perceive lecturers' differential treatment, depends on students' developmental level. In SDT, the measures of self are predicted to be mediators between lecturers behavior and students' academic behavior and outcomes, thus assuming that it is not lecturers' behaviour per say that influences students' motivation, but rather, how they perceive this behavior.

Results of a recent meta-analysis by Stroet et al. (2013) indicated that students' perceptions of need supportive teaching are generally positively related to their motivation and engagement. However, in the small body of studies that used observations or lecturer perceptions as a measure of need supportive teaching, much smaller associations or even no associations were found. This finding reveals that student perceptions of their relationship with their lecturer have a larger impact on motivation and engagement than the actual

lecturers' behavior. Lecturer-student relationship and its relation to academic achievement in different grade levels. The nature of the lecturer-student relationship and its meaning for students change over the school years. In transition to adolescence, there is a shift in students' orientation from relations with lecturers to increased peer orientation. Studies mostly report a decrease in the quality of lecturer-student relationships (Chang et al. 2004; Moritz Rudasill et al. 2010; O'Connor 2010) which may be attributed in part to changes in school context (more students in the class, higher school demands, and fewer opportunities for individual contact with lecturers) and partly to an increase in students' need for autonomy (Chang et al. 2004). But despite this decrease, students' relations with lecturers remain positively related to students' academic outcomes (Danielsen et al. 2010; Davidson et al. 2010; Niehaus et al. 2012).

Another aspect of age dependency in lecturer-student relationships is the development of students' capacity to perceive the differential lecturer behavior toward different students.

Developmental changes in students' social cognition also imply an increased capacity to perceive the differential lecturers treatment (Wentzel. 1998), thus assuming a moderating effect of students' age on the links between lecturer acceptance, student-perceived lecturer support, and achievement. However, research has mostly been focused on students at a single age, ignoring the age-related differences in the magnitude of the relation between lecturer perceptions and achievement.

In tertiary institutions as it relates to organizational justice and academic staff performance as baseline of interest, the majority of studies mentioned implied that the lecturer-student relationship was assumed to be a predictor and academic variables were seen as an outcome, that academic performance of students is influenced by relations with lecturers. In this study, three alternative explanations of the relation between lecturer-student relationships are explained in three forms (1) lecturer acceptance of students influences students' academic outcomes which is determined by the students' perceived personal support from their teachers. Mercer and DeRosier (2010) reported lecturer acceptance to be a predictor of students' perceptions of lecturer-student relationship quality. Students' ability to recognize the quality of lecturers' treatment is predicted to be crucial for the differences in students' academic achievement. (2) Lecturer acceptance of students mostly reflects actual student performance, which implies the opposite causal direction, namely, the influence of students' academic performance on lecturers' acceptance. Research shows that students with higher academic motivation, achievement, and self-regulation and stronger identity as student form better relations with their lecturers (Babad 1993; Davis 2006; Wentzel and Asher 1995). Thus, it is possible that lecturers just prefer students who are easier to work with and more rewarding for their effort. (3) The third possible explanation is the reciprocal model which assumes that, independently of the initial direction of causality, the relation between lecturer acceptance and students' academic outcomes becomes reciprocal, i.e. lecturers form more positive relations with students that achieve better, which influences students' perceived support from their teacher,

and this positive relation reinforces students' academic

performance. This is the relation that Skinner et al. (2008) described as "dynamics": the internal and external causal feedback loops that serve to promote or undermine the quality of children's performance in school over time. Students who are engaged and perform better receive more lecturer involvement than disaffected students, where lecturers increasingly withdraw their support and/or become more controlling in time. In that way, the initial dynamics are amplified (Hughes et al. 2008; Skinner and Belmont 1993). With regard to developmental changes in the lecturer-student relationship (e.g., Chang et al, 2004; MoritzRudasilletal.2010), it is clear that organizational justice in terms of interactional justice influences the degree of lecturer-student relationship in the institution which directly increases students' commitment and academic performance.

2.1.3. Relationship between Interactional Justice and Lecturer-student Relationship

Interactional justice involves considering interpersonal communication that links with procedures as fair. Interactional justice is a concept that concerns perceptions of employees about the treatment they have received during the application of organizational policies. According to Folger and Bies (1989), indicators of the existence of interactive justice are demonstrating due respect to employees, introducing consistent criteria, giving feedback on time and behaving appropriately and sincerely. Findings from the study conducted by Wasti (2001), the perception of positive interactive justice increases the positive teacher-student relationship that lecturers feel towards their institutions. With regards to interactive justice, Ajala (2000) asserted that the way a person perceives his surroundings influences that a person actually behaves and relates with people in that environment. In fact, a sense of interactive justice in the school workplace is dependent upon administrative behaviours such as equity, sensitivity to the plight of lecturers, respect, honesty and ethical interactions (Hoy & Miskel, 2005). Fox (2008), in his study, found that a positive interactive justice makes the school a good place to be, a satisfying and meaningful situation in which lecturers spend a substantial portion of their time relating and discussing academic issues with their students. This implies that lecturers from universities with better environment characterized with interactional justice, do better in research work, enjoy welfare scheme, have access to better teaching facilities, perform better and feel fulfilled than those with perceived negative interactive justice. Student perception plays an important role in incentive. In fact, research suggests that the most powerful predictor of a student motivation is the student's perception of control. Perceived control is the belief that one can determine one's behavior, influence one's environment, and bring about desired outcomes. Because students already have a history of experiences with whether lecturers are attuned to their needs, lecturers build on these experiences (Skinner & Greene, 2008). Therefore, a student's perception of the teacher's behavior impacts the relationship. Students who feel their teacher is not supportive and interactive towards them as a result of unfair treatment by management have less interest in learning and are less engaged in the classroom (Rimm-Kaufman and Sandilos, 2012). Students

read and perceive facial expression of their lecturer as they meet and interact daily in the classroom.

Employees seek justice when communicating with their managers and other relevant authorities in the organization. Interactional justice, based on peer to peer relationships, is the perception of justice among employees that is concerned with informing employees of the subjects of organizational decisions, as well as about attitudes and behaviors to which employees are exposed during the application of organizational decisions (Cohen-Charash and Spector, 2009; Liao and Tai, 2008). In other words, it expresses the quality of attitude and behaviors to which employees are exposed during the practice of (distributive and procedural) operations by managers (Greenberg, 2008; Liao and Tai, 2008). It is stated that interactional justice is composed of two sub-dimensions: interpersonal justice and informational justice (Cropanzano, 2007). Interpersonal justice points at the importance of kindness, respect and esteem in interpersonal relations, particularly in the relationships between employees and managers. Informational justice, on the other hand, is about informing employees properly and correctly in matters of organizational decision making. According to Cojuharenco and Patient (2013), employees focus on job results when they consider justice in the workplace, and they are likely to focus on the methods of communication and reciprocal relationships within the organization when they consider injustice. If the interactions of managers or manager representatives with employees occur in a just way, employees will respond with higher job performance (Settoon, 2008; Masterson, 2010; Cropanzano, 2007). Interactional justice can lead to strong interpersonal interactions and communication over time (Lerner, 2008; Cropanzano, 2007). According to social exchange theory, the positive or negative effect of employee-administration relationships on job performance stems from interactional justice (Cohen-Charash and Spector, 2009; Settoon, 2008; Wayne, 2010; Cropanzano 2007). According to this theory, if employees are satisfied with their relationships with the administration, apart from their formalized roles, they will volunteer to acquire additional roles, which will increase their contextual performance.

Interactional justice is a concept that emphasizes the quality of the relationships among employees in an organization. Interactional justice involves such behaviors as valuing employees, being respectful, and announcing a decision considered as a social value to employees (Çerli, 2010). Interactional justice claims that individuals are not only interested in the fairness of the process in assessing justice, but they are also interested in the behavior of the people authorized to manage this process (Çakmak, 2005). From this perspective, interactive justice is defined as the perceived justice of interpersonal behaviors during the application of processes (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2009). The classification of organizational justice by Donovan et al. (1998) approached it in two dimensions which are: Interpersonal justice and Informational justice. The relationship of employees to managers is inter-employee relationships. This may also be considered within interactional justice as the items included in this scale overlap with the characteristics of interactional justice.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

2.2.1. Leader-Member Exchange (LMX)

This study is anchored on leader-member exchange theory which describes organizational settings, aspects of the exchange relationship between a supervisor and a subordinate are considered to be fundamental to understanding employee attitudes and behavior (Napier & Ferris, 1993). Traditional leadership theories seek to explain leadership as a function of the personal characteristics of the leader, the features of the situation, or an interaction between the leader and the group (Gerstner & Day, 1997). These theories have failed to recognize that the relationship between a leader and a subordinate may have an impact upon the attitudes and behavior of the subordinate.

Dansereau, Graen, and Haga (1975) proposed that leader-member relationships are heterogeneous, that is, that the relationship between a leader and a member contained within a work unit are different, and that each leader-member relationship is a unique interpersonal relationship within an organizational structure. They coined the term vertical dyad linkage (VDL) to describe the dyadic relationship between a leader and a subordinate. VDL theory focuses on reciprocal influence processes within dyads. Graen (1976) also argued that research should focus on the behavior of the leader and the subordinate within the supervisor-subordinate dyad, rather than the supervisor and his other workgroup. Graen (1976) developed the theoretical base of the leader-member exchange model of leadership by building on role theory.

The theoretical basis of leader-member exchange theory is the concept of a developed or negotiated role. Dansereau, Graen, and Haga (1975), and Graen and Ferris (1993) initially conceptualized and tested the negotiating latitude construct in an investigation designed to study the assimilation of administrators into an organization. Negotiating latitude was defined as the extent to which a leader allows a member to identify his or her role development. This negotiating latitude was hypothesized as being central to the evolution of the quality of the leader-member exchange (Dansereau, Graen, and Haga, 1975).

Leader-member exchange theory is a subset of social exchange theory, and describes how leaders develop different exchange relationships over time with various subordinates of the same group (Dansereau, Graen, & Haga, 1975; Graen & Ferris, 1993). Thus, leader-member exchange refers to the exchanges between a subordinate and his or her leader. The leader-member exchange model provides an alternative approach to understanding the supervisor-subordinate relationship. The leader-member exchange model is based on the concept that role development will naturally result in differentiated role definitions and in varied leader-member exchanges. During initial interactions, supervisors and their subordinates engage in a role-making process, whereby the supervisor delegates the resources and responsibilities necessary to complete a task or duty. Subordinates who perform well on their task or duty will be perceived as more reliable by supervisors and, in turn, will be asked to perform more demanding roles (Dienesch & Linden, 1986). Leaders usually establish a special exchange relationship with a small number of trusted subordinates who function as assistants, lieutenants, or advisors. The exchange relationship established with remaining subordinates is substantially different (Yukl, 1994).

Much of the research on leader-member exchange divides the subordinate's roles and the quality of the leader-member exchange into two basic categories based on the leaders' and members' perceptions of the negotiating latitude: the in-group and the out-group (Dansereau, Graen & Haga, 1975; Graen, Napier & Ferris, 1993; Linden & Graen, 1980; Scandura & Graen, 1984; Vecchio, 1982). In-group or high-quality leader-member exchange is associated with high trust, interaction, support, and formal/informal rewards. In-group members are given more information by the supervisor and report greater job latitude. These in-group members make contributions that go beyond their formal job duties and take on responsibility for the completion of tasks that are most critical to the success of the unit (Linden & Graen, 1980). Conversely, out-group or low-quality leader-member exchange is characterized by low trust, interaction, support, and rewards. Out-group relationships involve those exchanges limited to the employment contract. In other words, out-group members perform the more routine, mundane tasks of the unit and experience a more formal exchange with the supervisor (Linden & Graen, 1980). Graen and Ferris (1993) and Linden and Graen (1980) provide evidence that in-group and out-group memberships tend to develop fairly quickly and remain stable.

Similarly, social exchange theory (Emerson, 1962) recognizes how dyadic relations develop within a social context. Social exchange theory describes how power and influence among leaders and members are conditioned on the availability of alternative exchange partners from whom these leaders and members can obtain valued resources. Blau (1964) also distinguished the differences between social and economic exchange, noting that social exchange tends to produce feelings of personal obligation, gratitude, and trust, whereas economic exchange does not. This distinction between social and economic exchange is fundamental to the way in which out-group or low quality exchanges and in-group or high quality exchanges have been distinguished in leader-member exchange research (Linden & Graen, 1980; Linden, Wayne, & Stilwell, 1993). Low quality leader member relations have been characterized in terms of economic exchanges that do not progress beyond the employment contract, whereas high quality leader-member relations have been characterized by social exchanges that extend beyond the employment contract.

This relevance of the theory to the work is based on the premise that it meditates the relationship of distributive justice-employee performance in organization. Leader-member exchange theory and its relationship are embedded in social exchange and, in return, it is an obligation for subordinates that they have to reciprocate the high quality relationship with their managers\leaders.

2.3. Empirical Review

Ogwuche and Apeiker (2016) conducted a study on influence of interactional justice and organizational support on organizational commitment among academic staff of Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine the influence of interactional justice on organizational support and commitment among academic staff. The study adopted a cross sectional design. A total of 221 respondents were selected. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using regression model. Findings revealed that organizational support has a

significant joint influence on organizational commitment among lecturers. A significant joint influence exists between organizational support and interactional justice among lecturers and interactional justice positively influence organizational commitment. The study concluded that organizational support and interactional justice have significant joint influence on organizational commitment. This implies that organizational support and interactional justice are co-determinants of organizational commitment among lecturers. It therefore, means that high level of university support with a corresponding appreciable level of interactional justice can give rise to high organizational commitment among lecturers, whereas, low level of organizational support coupled with insignificant level of interactional justice may lead to decline in level of commitment among lecturers. The study recommended that management of Nigerian universities should come out with supportive policies as a way of motivating lecturers to be committed to their academic work.

A study on organizational justice and job performance of lecturers in federal universities in South South Zone of Nigeria was conducted by Efanga, Aniedi and Identa (2015). The objective of the study was to determine the relationship between organizational justice and lecturers' participation in co-curricular activities, involvement in community service and lecturers' teaching behavior in the selected universities in South South, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. A sample size of 529 lecturers was selected from a total population of 5664 lecturers as at 2013/2014 session. Data were gathered from questionnaire administered and thus analyzed using simple regression model. The results revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between organizational justice and lecturers' participation in co-curricular activities in the selected universities in the South South zone of Nigeria. Also, a significant relationship exist between organizational justice and lecturers' involvement in community service in the selected universities in the South South zone of Nigeria. Finally, lecturers' teaching behaviour is significant and positively related with organizational justice among lecturers in the selected universities in the South South zone of Nigeria. The study concluded that lecturers' participation in co-curricular activities, lecturers' involvement in community service and lecturers' teaching behavior are determinants of lecturers' job performance which is influenced by the degree of implementation of organizational justice in the institutions. The study recommended that university management should implement equitable reward system in the universities in order to improve lecturers' morale and productivity.

Usikalu, Ogunleye and Effiong (2015) conducted a study on organizational justice, job satisfaction and employee performance among Teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study focused on examining the influence of the dimensions of organizational justice on job satisfaction and job performance among teachers in Ekiti State. The descriptive survey design was employed and data were collected through questionnaire. Two hundred and fifty eight (258) teachers randomly drawn from Ekiti State public schools participated in the study. Four hypotheses were tested using the independent t-test and the two way Analysis of Variance. Results showed that organizational justice significantly influences job performance among teachers in Ekiti State.

Also, it was revealed that job satisfaction significantly influenced job performance among teachers. However, no significant interaction effect of job satisfaction and organizational justice was found on employee performance. Result of data analyses also showed that sex has no significant influence on employee performance among teachers in Ekiti State. The study recommended that teachers should be given responsibilities and authority with less supervision to boost their sense of belongingness, respect and commitment which sustains justice in organizations and enhance performance.

Baghini, Pourkiani, and Abbasi (2014) conducted a study on the relationship between organizational justice and Productive behaviour of staff in Refaah bank branches in Kerman City. To analyze the collected data, the descriptive statistics and Pearson’s correlational test were used. Results show that there is a significant relationship between components of organizational justice and productive behavior of staff in Refaah bank branches in Kerman City.

Ajmi (1998) investigated the analysis of the relationship between organizational loyalty and workers’ feelings with organizational justice in banking sector in India. The objective of the study was to examine the relationship between organizational loyalty and employees’ perception of procedural justice and distributive justice in banking sector

in India. The study employed survey research design with a sample of 117 employees selected from 24 banks in India. The data were collected through questionnaire and Correlation and regression were used for the analysis. The study found that there is a low feeling with procedural justice, all the workers have a feeling of inequity in the application of laws and administrative decisions, as well as the low feeling in distributive justice which do not relate with organizational loyalty. The study recommended that managers should apply laws and administrative decisions as they relate to organizational justice to avoid the feeling of inequity among employees in the same job cadre in order to enhance organizational loyalty in the banking sector.

3. Methods

This study employed survey research design to collect primary data through administration of instrument of questionnaires to respondents drawn from selected universities from south-south of Nigeria. Information was gathered from a cross-section of 400 respondents from fourteen universities which comprised seven each of public and private in the region. Data were analysed using factorial analysis of variance technique with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20 to determine the relationship between distributive justice and academic staff performance among the universities in the south-south of Nigeria.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages will be used in answering the research question. This hypothesis is tested using the factorial analysis of variance to find the level of differences between interactional justice and academic staff performance among the universities in the south-south of Nigeria. All the 400 copies of questionnaire distributed were properly completed and returned. Thus, the return rate is 100%. Therefore 400 respondents that participated in the study were used in the analyses.

Table 1: Respondent Biodata

Category	Responses	Response rate	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	289		72.3
	Female	111		27.7
	Total	400		100
Age	26-35yrs	97		24.3
	36-45yrs	110		27.5
	46-55yrs	87		21.7
	Above 55yrs	106		26.5
Marital Status	Single	45		11.3
	Married	330		82.5
	Divorced	25		6.3
	Total	400		100
Educational Qualification	B.Sc/HND	10		2.5
	MBA/M.Sc	40		10.0
	Ph.D	310		77.5
	Total	400		100
Working Experience	Below 1yr	11		2.7
	2-6yrs	107		26.7
	7-11yrs	96		24.0
	12-16yrs	95		23.7
	Above 16yrs	91		22.7
	Total	400		100

Source: Field Survey, (2020).

In all, respondents from government institutions accounted for 54.3% of the entire respondents. Table 1 presents a summary of the responses on the distribution of respondents into their various categories of gender, age bracket, marital status, educational qualification and working experience,.

Gender Distribution: Table 1 indicates that 289 respondents (72.3%) are males, while 111 respondents (27.7%) are females. This indicates that there are more male lecturers in the selected tertiary institutions examined than there are female lecturers.

Age Bracket Distribution: Table 1 indicates that 97 respondents (24.3%) are within the age bracket of 26-35 years of age; 110 respondents (27.5%) are within the age bracket of 36-45 years of age, 87 respondents (21.7%) fall within the age bracket of 46-55 years, the remaining 106 respondents (26.5%) is above 55 years of age. This indicates that greater portion of academic staff is within the age bracket of 36-45 years.

Marital Status Distribution: Table 1 indicates that 45 respondents (11.3%) are singles, 330 respondents (82.5%) are married while 25 respondents (6.3%) are divorced. This implies that there are more married academic staff than there are academic staff that are still single and divorcees.

Educational Qualification: Table 1 shows that the number of respondents with B.Sc/HND is 10 constituting 2.5%, MBA/M.Sc is 40 (10.0%). PhD has 310 (77.5%). From the Table, the respondents that has PhD has the highest percentage. It is understandable because of the necessity of PhD in the University teaching profession.

Working Experience: Table 1 shows the number of years that the respondents have put in the industry. Experience is important to the study because people that are new in the industry may likely not provide the right answers to questions posed in the questionnaire. The Table shows that respondents that have spent between 7-11 years in the industry are highest in number with 96 respondents constituting 24.0% of the entire respondents followed by people that have spent between 2-6 years 107 (26.7%). Respondents that have spent below 1 year are 11 (1.8%), respondents that have spent between 12-16 years are 95, constituting 23.7%, while those that have spent above 16 years are 91 (22.7%). The Table shows that most of the respondents have spent reasonable number of years in the Universities to adequately evaluate and appropriately rate their experiences in the Universities.

Table 2: Interactional Justice Descriptive Statistics

Scale Items	Federal			State			Private		
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
When decisions are made about my job, the head always considers my interest	263	3.83	1.06	76	3.72	1.09	285	3.64	1.10
When decisions are made about my job, the head considers my personal needs with the greatest care.	263	3.77	1.09	76	3.71	1.11	285	3.72	1.12
My head explains clearly any decisions if it is related to my job.	263	3.83	1.10	76	3.80	1.05	285	3.62	1.11
I receive cordial working relationship from my HOD and colleagues	263	3.82	1.08	76	3.76	1.07	285	3.69	1.13
I can confidently say that my institution keeps my interest in mind when making decisions.	263	3.84	1.11	76	3.64	1.03	285	3.66	1.11
Valid N (listwise)	263		76			285			

Source: Field computation, (2020).

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation responses on the difference level of application of interactional justice applied by management in dealing with academic staff. On the issue of whether academic staff believe that when decisions are made about my job, the head always considers their interest, the federal university has a mean score of 3.83 while the standard deviation is 1.06; states university has a mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation is 1.09 while the private university has a mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation of 1.10 which is accepted. Also the idea whether the academic staff in their respective Universities believe that when decisions are made about their jobs, the heads consider their personal needs with the greatest care the federal university has a mean score of 3.77 and the standard deviation of 1.09; states university has a mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation is 1.11 while the private university has a mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation of 1.12 which is accepted. On the assertion whether the academic staff feel that their heads explain clearly any decisions if it is related to their jobs, the federal university has a mean score of 3.83 and the standard deviation of 1.10; states university has a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation is 1.05 while the private university has a mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.11 which is accepted. On the idea to ascertain whether academic staff feel that they receive cordial working relationship from their HODs and colleagues, the federal university has a mean score of 3.82 and the standard deviation of 1.08; states university has a mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation is 1.07 while the private university has a mean score of 3.69 and standard deviation of 1.13 which is accepted. Finally, on the idea to ascertain whether academic staff believed that they can confidently say that their institution keeps their interest in mind when making decisions the federal university has a mean score of 3.84 and the standard deviation of 1.11; states university has a mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation is 1.03 while the private university has a mean score of 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.11 which is accepted. The mean scores show that

academic staff from both universities perceived the level of informational justice to be high in their universities, with a mean score above 3.5 in 5 points scale.

Table 3: Lecturer Student Relationship Descriptive Statistics

Scale Items	Federal			State			Private		
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel i am close to my students and i can trust them	263	3.69	1.07	76	3.81	1.09	285	4.10	.96
I get along with my students to a large extent	263	3.70	1.09	76	3.85	1.01	285	4.12	.89
What i teach at school is really interesting to my students	263	3.60	1.13	76	3.81	1.11	285	4.14	.89
I am willing to invest more time for all the courses due to the favourable feedback i get from my students	263	3.65	1.10	76	3.85	.99	285	4.13	.95
I am satisfied with the performance of my students	263	3.66	1.15	76	3.78	.97	285	4.19	.90
Valid N (listwise)	263			76			285		

Source: Field Computation, (2020).

Table 3 shows the responses of that sought to assess the level of lecturer-students' relationship in the studied Universities. On the issue on whether academic staff feel they are close to the students and can trust them, the federal university has a mean score of 3.69 while the standard deviation is 1.07; states university has a mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation is 1.09 while the private university has a mean score of 4.10 and standard deviation of 0.96 which is accepted. Also the idea whether the academic staff believe that they get along with my students to a large extent, the federal university has a mean score of 3.70 and the standard deviation of 1.09; states university has a mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation is 1.01 while the private university has a mean score of 4.12 and standard deviation of 0.89 which is accepted. On the assertion whether the academic staff feel that what they teach at school is really interesting to their students, the federal university has a mean score of 3.60 and the standard deviation of 1.13; states university has a mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation is 1.11 while the private university has a mean score of 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.89 which is accepted. On the idea to ascertain whether academic staff believe that they are willing to invest more time for all the courses due to the favourable feedback they get from the students, the federal university has a mean score of 3.65 and the standard deviation of 1.10; states university has a mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation is 0.99 while the private university has a mean score of 4.13 and standard deviation of 0.95 which is accepted. Finally, on the idea to ascertain whether academic staff believe that they are satisfied with the performance of their students, the federal university has a mean score of 3.66 and the standard deviation of 1.15; states university has a mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation is 0.97 while the private university has a mean score of 4.19 and standard deviation of 0.90 which is accepted. The mean scores show that academic staff from both universities perceived high level of lecturer-student relationship in their universities, with a mean score above 3.5 in 5 points scale. Interestingly, private university has the highest mean score (4.00). It therefore seems that academic staff working in private universities have more cordial relationship with their students more than those in both Federal and State Universities.

4.1. Test of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis One

H_{04} : There is no level of variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturers-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-south Nigeria.

H_{A4} : There is level of variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturers-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-south Nigeria.

Table 4: Tests of Difference between Interactional Justice and Lecturer-Students' Relationships

Dependent Variable: Lectstudent Relations						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	137.690 ^a	33	4.172	6.062	.000	.253
Intercept	2151.350	1	2151.350	3125.503	.000	.841
Students' Relationship	39.844	2	19.922	28.943	.000	.089
Interactional Justice	4.170	11	.379	.551	.868	.010
Public/Private universities *Interactional Justice	13.258	20	.663	.963	.506	.032
Error	406.110	590	.688			
Total	9104.870	624				
Corrected Total	543.800	623				

a. R Squared = .253 (Adjusted R Squared = .211)				
a. R Squared = .253 (Adjusted R Squared = .211)				
(I) Public/private university	(J) Public/private university	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Federal	State	-.6203*	.10805	.000
	Private	-.9306*	.07094	.000
State	Federal	.6203*	.10805	.000
	Private	-.3104*	.10711	.001
Private	Federal	.9306*	.07094	.000
	State	.3104*	.10711	.001

Hypothesis four was also tested using factorial analysis of variance. The variables understudy in the universities (Federal, State and Private) were interactional justice as the independent variable and lecturer-students' relationships as dependent variable. The result is presented in table 4, the model fit was established ($F = 28.943$, $P < 0.000$). The result shows a significant association between the universities and lecturer-students' relationship ($F = 0.551$, $P < 0.868$). In other words, the level of lecturers' students' relationship depends on whether the university is public or private. Interactional justice is significantly associated with lecturer students' relationships. Similarly, the interaction between university status and interactional justice produced a significant effect on lecturers' students' relationship among the universities in the South South, Nigeria ($F = 0.963$, $P < 0.506$).

The examination of partial Eta square shows that the proportion of variance due to between group are 0.089, 0.010, and 0.032 for private/public universities, interactional justice, interaction between private/public universities and interactional justice respectively. Thus, the effect is small and corroborated by R2 (R-Square = 0.117 or 11.7%).

The evaluation of pair wise mean differences shows a significant difference mean score of lecturer students' relationship in public universities and private universities (Federal and private $P < 0.001$, State and Private $P < 0.021$). From the result presented in table 4, we accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is level of variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturers-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-south Nigeria.

4.2. Results

The result of the test revealed that the mean scores of interactional justice are also close. It shows that Federal has 3.82 mean score, 3.73 for state and 3.67 for private universities while the mean scores on the level of lecturer-student relationship in the federal, state and private universities are 3.66; 3.82 and 4.13. These showed that the level of lecturer student relationship is at its best since the results seem to cut across both public and private universities as the differences among the mean scores seems negligible. In the hypothesis the result shows that there is a level of variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturers-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-south Nigeria, ($F = 28.943$, $P < 0.000$). Interactional justice is significantly associated with lecturer students' relationships ($F = 0.551$, $P < 0.868$). Similarly, the variation of academic staff on interactional justice produced a significant effect on lecturers' students' relationship among the universities in the South South, Nigeria ($F = 0.963$, $P < 0.506$).

The examination of partial Eta square shows that the proportion of variance due to (between) group are 0.089, 0.010, and 0.032 for university management interactional justice, lecturer-student relationship and interactional justice perception by lecturers respectively. Thus, the effect is small and corroborated by R2 (R-Square = 0.117 or 11.7%). The evaluation of pairwise mean differences shows a significant difference mean score of lecturer students' relationship in public universities and private universities (Federal and private $P < 0.001$, State and Private $P < 0.021$). From the result, we accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a level of variation in interactional justice

in relation to lecturers-students' relationship between academic staff in public and private universities in South-south Nigeria.

This finding implies that there is a significant variation in interactional justice in relation to lecturer students' between academic staff in public and private universities in South South, Nigeria. In congruence with the results of this hypothesis as supported by Hoy and Miskel, (2005); Fox (2008) found that a positive interactive justice makes the school a good place to be, a satisfying and meaningful situation in which lecturers spend a substantial portion of their time relating and discussing academic issues with their students.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1. Conclusion

This study explores academic staff perceptions toward organizational justice and how it varies between academic staff in public and private universities in South-South, Nigeria in terms of commitment, subject knowledge, communication skills and lecturer-student relationship. In the course of this study, theories and empirical literature were reviewed, data were collected and tested. From the research it is ascertained that organisational justice led to different variation of academic staff performance between public and private universities in South-South, Nigeria. These results build on the work of previous researchers who demonstrated that organizational justice influences academic staff performance through different behaviours. This clearly shows that when perceived organisational justice exist in the university environment, there is the generation of strong feeling of obligation towards their respective institutions and academic staff become more

committed to their job. Therefore, it can be deduced that equitable distribution of resources, fair procedures for job decisions, with appropriate allocation of resources and fair communication of decisions will result in high academic staff performance toward higher academic excellence.

5.2. Recommendation

On the basis of the findings and conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendation is made.

1. Management of Nigerian universities should come out with supportive policies as a way of promoting interactional justice toward maintaining lecturer-student relationship which can be done through integrating the philosophy of target education programme established in 1990 by Aumua and Drake (2002) and the French Intervention programme (Chouinard, 2004-2005, CLASSE) which will both give practical tools to favour respective and harmonious Lecturer-Student Relationship as well as to enhance achievement of academic staff performance through organizational justice.

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